

**ON THE LEAST SIGNIFICANT 2-ADIC AND TERNARY DIGITS
OF CERTAIN STIRLING NUMBERS**

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Abstract

Our main goal is to effectively calculate the p -ary digits of certain Stirling numbers of the second kind. We base our study on an observation regarding these numbers: as m increases, more and more p -adic digits match in $S(i(p-1)p^m, k)$ with integer $i \geq 1$.

1. Introduction

Let n and k be positive integers, p be a prime, $d_p(k)$ and $\nu_p(k)$ denote the sum of digits in the base p representation of k and the highest power of p dividing k , i.e., the p -adic order of k , respectively. For the rational n/k we set $\nu_p(n/k) = \nu_p(n) - \nu_p(k)$. In 1808, Legendre showed

Lemma 1. ([2]) *For any positive integer k , we have $\nu_p(k!) = (k - d_p(k))/(p - 1)$.*

We define the 2-free part of $k!$ (or unit factor of $k!$ with respect to 2), b_k , as

$$k! = 2^{k-d_2(k)} b_k,$$

or more explicitly,

$$b_k = \prod_{\substack{3 \leq p \leq k \\ p \text{ prime}}} p^{\frac{k-d_p(k)}{p-1}}.$$

In general, b_k is the p -free part of $k!$ (or unit factor of $k!$ with respect to p), i.e., $k! = p^{\frac{k-d_p(k)}{p-1}} b_k$ with

$$b_k = \prod_{\substack{2 \leq p' \leq k \\ p' \neq p \text{ and prime}}} p'^{\frac{k-d_{p'}(k)}{p'-1}}.$$

We have the identity (cf. [1]) for the Stirling numbers of the second kind

$$S(n, k) = \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} (-1)^j (k-j)^n.$$

Our main goal is to effectively calculate the p -ary digits of certain Stirling numbers of the second kind. For example, if $k = 2$ then $S(m, 2) = 2^{m-1} - 1, m \geq 2$; thus, the binary representation consists of all ones. We try to find similar properties for other values of k . We base our study on an observation (cf. [6]) regarding these numbers: as m increases, more and more p -adic digits match in $S(i(p - 1)p^m, k)$ with integer $i \geq 1$.

We claim the main results (cf. Theorems 2, 4, and 5) in Section 2, and illustrate and prove them in Sections 3-5. We discuss the case with $p = 2$ in Sections 3 and 4 and derive additional results (cf. Lemmas 8 and 9). A general approach is presented in Section 4. Options and limitations (cf. Theorems 12-18 based on [4] and [6]) for other primes are discussed in Section 5. Two examples are provided to demonstrate the cases of 2-adic and ternary digits.

2. Main Results

First, we deal with the binary digits and obtain

Theorem 2. *With the above introduced notation,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 S(2^m i, k) &\equiv \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{\substack{j=0 \\ k-j \text{ odd}}}^k \binom{k}{j} (-1)^j (k-j)^{2^m i} \\
 &\equiv 2^{d_2(k)-1} (-1)^{k-1} b_k^{2^m-1} \pmod{2^{m+2-k+d_2(k)}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

for $m + 2 \geq k - d_2(k)$, $m \geq 2$, and $i \geq 1$.

Remark 3. Recall that (2.1) implies that $\nu_2(S(2^m i, k)) = d_2(k) - 1$ if $d_2(k) - 1 < m + 2 - k + d_2(k)$, i.e., $m \geq k - 2$, cf. [5] and [7] for the generalized version.

We make the calculation more explicit in Theorem 4 and generalize it for $p = 3$ in Theorem 5, and in Theorems 12 and 17, in general.

We set $u_k \equiv b_k \equiv b_k^{-1} \pmod{4}$ to be the least positive residue of the 2-free part b_k of $k!$ modulo 4 which is the same as that of its inverse modulo 4,

$$c_k = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{if } u_k = 3, \\ +1, & \text{if } u_k = 1, \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_k = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{b_k}{4} \rceil, & \text{if } u_k = 3, \\ \lceil \frac{b_k}{4} \rceil - 1, & \text{if } u_k = 1, \end{cases} \tag{2.2}$$

which yields that $b_k = 4a_k + c_k$. We end up with the following theorem that gives $S(2^m i, k)$ explicitly, modulo a high power of two, and in terms of k , m , and r ($r \geq 0$ integer).

Theorem 4. *With the above introduced notation, for $k \geq 3$ we have*

$$S(2^m i, k) \equiv 2^{d_2(k)-1} (-1)^{k-1} c_k \sum_{j=0}^r (-4c_k a_k)^j \pmod{2^{e(m,k,r)}} \tag{2.3}$$

with $e(m, k, r) = \min\{m + 2 - k + d_2(k), (r + 1)(2 + \nu_2(a_k)) + d_2(k) - 1\}$.

With $p = 3$, we set $u_k \equiv b_k \equiv b_k^{-1} \pmod{p}$ to be the least positive residue of the p -free part b_k of $k!$ modulo p which is the same that of its inverse modulo p ,

$$c_k = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{if } u_k = p - 1, \\ +1, & \text{if } u_k = 1, \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_k = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{b_k}{p} \rceil, & \text{if } u_k = p - 1, \\ \lceil \frac{b_k}{p} \rceil - 1, & \text{if } u_k = 1, \end{cases}$$

which yields that $b_k = p \cdot a_k + c_k$. We get that

Theorem 5. *For $p = 3$ and $k \equiv 2$ or $4 \pmod{6}$, we have*

$$S(i(p - 1)p^m, k) \equiv p^{\frac{d_p(k)}{p-1}-1} (-1)^{\frac{kp}{p-1}} c_k \sum_{j=0}^r (-pc_k a_k)^j \pmod{p^{e(m,k,r)}} \tag{2.4}$$

where

$$e(m, k, r) = \min\left\{m + 1 - \frac{k - d_p(k)}{p - 1}, m + 1 + \nu_p(a_k) + \frac{d_p(k)}{p - 1} - 1, (r + 1)(1 + \nu_p(a_k)) + \frac{d_p(k)}{p - 1} - 1\right\}.$$

3. Proof of Theorem 2

We need a well-known theorem and two lemmas.

Theorem 6. (Kummer, 1852) *The power of a prime p that divides the binomial coefficient $\binom{n}{k}$ is given by the number of carries when we add k and $n - k$ in base p .*

The first lemma is an improvement of the Fermat–Euler Theorem which claims only that $t^{2^{m+1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{2^{m+2}}$ for $p = 2, m \geq 0$, and $t \geq 1$ odd.

Lemma 7. (Lemma 3 in [3]) *For any integer $m \geq 1$ and any odd integer t ,*

$$t^{2^m} \equiv 1 \pmod{2^{m+2}}.$$

This lemma can be proven by induction on m and further generalized to higher 2-power moduli (cf. [3]). The following lemma is an improvement of the well-known congruence $\binom{p^t-1}{j} \equiv (-1)^j \pmod p, 0 \leq j \leq p^t - 1$ for prime p and $t \geq 1$ integer.

Lemma 8. *If p is a prime, $(a, p) = 1, t \geq 1$, and $1 \leq j \leq p^t - 1$, then*

$$\nu_p \left(\binom{ap^t}{j} \right) = t - \nu_p(j) \tag{3.1}$$

and

$$\binom{ap^t - 1}{j} \equiv (-1)^j \pmod{p^{t - \lfloor \log_p j \rfloor}}.$$

Proof. Clearly, identity (3.1) is true by Theorem 6. Using the fact that $\binom{ap^t-1}{0} = 1$ and

$$\binom{ap^t}{j} = \binom{ap^t - 1}{j - 1} + \binom{ap^t - 1}{j},$$

it implies that

$$\binom{ap^t - 1}{j} \equiv (-1)^j \pmod{p^{t - \lfloor \log_p j \rfloor}}$$

by step-by-step increasing j from $j = 1$ on. □

Proof of Theorem 2. The proof relies on the fact that terms with $k - j$ even will not contribute to the congruence since $2^m i \geq m + 2$ as $m \geq 2$, and on Lemma 7, since

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{\substack{j=0 \\ k-j \text{ odd}}}^k \binom{k}{j} (-1)^j (k-j)^{2^m i} &\equiv \frac{1}{k!} (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{\substack{j=0 \\ k-j \text{ odd}}}^k \binom{k}{j} \\ &\equiv \frac{(-1)^{k-1} 2^{k-1}}{2^{k-d_2(k)} b_k} \pmod{2^{m+2-k+d_2(k)}}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that since b_k is odd, $b_k^{-1} \equiv b_k^{2^m-1} \pmod{2^{m+2}}$ by Lemma 7. □

We note that it is easy to see that

$$S(n, 5) = \frac{1}{24} (5^{n-1} - 4^n + 2 \cdot 3^n - 2^{n+1} + 1) \tag{3.2}$$

holds which yields

$$S(2^m i, 5) \equiv 2 \cdot 15^{2^m-1} \pmod{2^{m-1}} \tag{3.3}$$

for $i, m \geq 1$. Indeed, we have

$$3^{-1} \equiv 3^{2^m-1} \equiv 3^{2^m i-1} \pmod{2^{m+2}},$$

$$5^{-1} \equiv 5^{2^m-1} \equiv 5^{2^m i-1} \pmod{2^{m+2}}$$

and

$$S(2^m i, 5) \equiv \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{5} (5^{2^m i} + 10 \cdot 3^{2^m i} + 5) \equiv \frac{1}{15} \cdot \frac{1}{8} 16 \equiv 2 \cdot 15^{2^m - 1} \pmod{2^{m-1}}$$

by identity (3.2) and Lemma 7, if $m \geq 1$ and $i \geq 1$, with direct calculations and without using Theorem 2. Moreover, we get

Lemma 9. *For any integer $r \geq 0$ and $i, m \geq 1$, we have*

$$S(2^m i, 5) \equiv -2 \sum_{j=0}^r 2^{4j} \pmod{2^{\min\{m-1, 4r+5\}}}. \tag{3.4}$$

Proof of Lemma 9. In fact, the statement holds if $2^m i < 5$. Otherwise, we rewrite

$$\begin{aligned} 15^{2^m - 1} &= (4^2 - 1)^{2^m - 1} = -1 + \binom{2^m - 1}{1} 4^2 - \binom{2^m - 1}{2} 4^4 + \dots \\ &\equiv - \sum_{j=0}^r 2^{4j} \pmod{2^{\min\{m+4, 4r+4\}}} \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 8, which already implies (3.4) by (3.3) since $m+2-k+d_2(k) = m-1$. \square

The congruence (3.4) guarantees that the binary representation of $S(2^m i, 5)$ ends in $(0111)^*011110$ if m is large enough. (With d being any finite word formed over the alphabet $\{0, 1\}$, $(d)^*$ denotes any finite number $t, t \geq 0$, of copies of the “word” d .) If $r = 0$ and $m \geq 6$ then we have

$$S(2^m i, 5) \equiv 30 \pmod{32}.$$

If $r \geq (m - 6)/4$ then the congruence (3.4) turns into

$$S(2^m i, 5) \equiv -2 \sum_{j=0}^r 2^{4j} \pmod{2^{m-1}},$$

and the terms beyond $j = \lceil (m - 6)/4 \rceil$ effectively do not contribute to the sum.

4. 2-adic Digits: A General Approach for Effective Calculation and the Proof of Theorem 4

If $k = 5$ then we get $d_2(5) = 2, b_5 = 15$ and $S(2^m i, 5)$ satisfies congruence (3.3) by Theorem 2. For larger values of k , we use (4.1) below since we do not need the exact value of b_k . In fact, to effectively calculate $S(2^m i, k)$ modulo a large 2-power, it suffices to use b_k modulo that 2-power. It can be calculated by the congruence

$$b_k = \frac{k!}{p^{\sum_{j \geq 1} \lfloor \frac{k}{p^j} \rfloor}} \equiv \delta^{\sum_{j \geq q} \lfloor \frac{k}{p^j} \rfloor} \prod_{j \geq 0} (K_j!)_p \pmod{p^q}, \tag{4.1}$$

with $\delta = \delta(p^q) = -1$ except if $p = 2, q \geq 3$ when $\delta = 1$, K_j is the least positive residue of $\lfloor k/p^j \rfloor \pmod{p^q}, 0 \leq j \leq d$, if $p^d \leq k < p^{d+1}$, and

$$(K!)_p = \frac{K!}{p^{\lfloor \frac{K}{p} \rfloor} \lfloor \frac{K}{p} \rfloor!}$$

is the product of those positive integers not exceeding K that are not divisible by p ; cf. [2, Proposition 1, p8]. With $p = 2$, we have $\delta = 1$ if q is large enough. This implies that

$$b_k \equiv \prod_{j \geq 0} (K_j!)_2 \pmod{2^q}.$$

Now we can gain a more in-depth look at the binary digits of $S(2^m i, k)$ by evaluating the right-hand side of (2.1) more effectively via Theorem 4.

Proof of Theorem 4. In a similar fashion to the case with $k = 5$ and depending upon $u_k \pmod{4}$, we rewrite

$$\begin{aligned} b_k^{2^m-1} &= (4a_k + c_k)^{2^m-1} = c_k + \binom{2^m-1}{1} (4a_k) c_k^2 + \binom{2^m-1}{2} (4a_k)^2 (c_k)^3 + \dots \\ &\equiv c_k \sum_{j=0}^r (-4a_k c_k)^j \pmod{2^{\min\{m+2+\nu_2(a_k), (r+1)(2+\nu_2(a_k))\}}} \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 8, which already implies (2.3) by Theorem 2 since $\min\{m + 2 - k + d_2(k), m + 2 + \nu_2(a_k) + d_2(k) - 1, (r + 1)(2 + \nu_2(a_k)) + d_2(k) - 1\} = \min\{m + 2 - k + d_2(k), (r + 1)(2 + \nu_2(a_k)) + d_2(k) - 1\}$. \square

Example 10. For $k = 3, 4, 5$, and 7 , we get $b_3 = b_4 = 3, b_5 = 15, b_7 = 315, u_k = 3, c_k = -1, a_3 = a_4 = 1, a_5 = 4$, and $a_7 = 79$, which yield that

$$\begin{aligned} S(2^m i, 3) &\equiv -2 \sum_{j=0}^r 4^j \pmod{2^{\min\{m+1, 2(r+1)+1\}}}, \\ S(2^m i, 4) &\equiv \sum_{j=0}^r 4^j \pmod{2^{\min\{m-1, 2(r+1)\}}}, \\ S(2^m i, 5) &\equiv -2 \sum_{j=0}^r 16^j \pmod{2^{\min\{m-1, 4(r+1)+1\}}}, \end{aligned}$$

in agreement with (3.4), and

$$S(2^m i, 7) \equiv -2^2 \sum_{j=0}^r 316^j \pmod{2^{\min\{m-2, 2(r+1)+2\}}}.$$

On the other hand, if $k = 6$ then $b_6 = 45$, $u_6 = 1$, $c_6 = 1$, $a_6 = 11$, and

$$S(2^m i, 6) \equiv -2^2 \sum_{j=0}^r (-44)^j \pmod{2^{\min\{m-2, 2(r+1)+1\}}}.$$

Remark 11. Note that the “best use” of the congruence (2.3) comes with values of a_k that are powers of two, e.g., if $k = 3, 4, 5$, etc. It will be interesting to see the general solution to this problem, i.e., find all k so that a_k , which is derived from the 2-free part b_k of $k!$ by (2.2), is a power of two. Indeed, beyond the small cases, we look for any $k \geq 4$, for which $k!$ is the difference or sum of two powers of two (depending on the sign of c_k), or equivalently, whose binary representation is of the form $1(0)^*1(0)^*0$ or $1(1)^*(0)^*0$. This follows by the identity $k! = 2^{k-d_2(k)} b_k = 2^{k-d_2(k)}(4a_k + c_k)$. (Of course, for $k \geq 2$, we get an even $k!$ so it must end with a binary zero.)

5. Other primes

As m increases, more and more p -adic digits match in $S(i(p-1)p^m, k)$. However, to effectively calculate these matching digits we need another approach. We rely on papers [4] and [6]. We need the following combination of Lemma 5 and Theorem 3 of [4]. This helps in generalizing Theorem 4 for odd primes if k is divisible by $p-1$.

Theorem 12. ([4]) *For any odd prime p , integer t , $n = i(p-1)p^m$, $1 \leq k \leq n$, and $m > \frac{k}{p-1} - 2$, we have*

$$(-1)^{k+1} k! S(n, k) \equiv \sum_{p|i} \binom{k}{i} (-1)^i \pmod{p^{m+1}} \tag{5.1}$$

and

$$\sum_{i \equiv t \pmod{p}} \binom{k}{i} (-1)^i \equiv \begin{cases} (-1)^{\frac{k}{p-1}-1} p^{\frac{k}{p-1}-1} \pmod{p^{\frac{k}{p-1}}}, & \text{if } k \text{ is divisible by } p-1, \\ 0 \pmod{p^{\lfloor \frac{k}{p-1} \rfloor}}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \tag{5.2}$$

Therefore, if k is divisible by $p-1$ then

$$S(n, k) \equiv p^{\frac{d_p(k)}{p-1}-1} (-1)^{\frac{kp}{p-1}} b_k^{-1} \pmod{p^{\min\{m+1-\frac{k-d_p(k)}{p-1}, \frac{d_p(k)}{p-1}\}}}$$

where b_k is the p -free part of $k!$ as defined in the introduction and by the Fermat-Euler Theorem

$$b_k^{-1} \equiv b_k^{(p-1)p^m-1} \pmod{p^{m+1}}.$$

Remark 13. Note that the p -adic order of $S(i(p-1)p^m, k)$ does not depend on i and m . This does not exclude the possibility that by increasing m we can get more insight into the base p representation of $S(i(p-1)p^m, k)$. Indeed, if $p = 2$ then (2.1) provides us with the right tool since $\sum_{2|i} \binom{k}{i} (-1)^i = 2^{k-1}$, and it leads to Theorem 4. However, in general, increasing m does not help in getting more p -ary digits in a computationally effective way, for (5.2) cannot be significantly improved; although, according to Theorem 17, we get more and more matching digits in $S(i(p-1)p^m, k)$ and $S(i(p-1)p^{m+1}, k)$ (starting with the least significant bit). We can avoid the use of (5.2) if a closed form exists for $\sum_{p|i} \binom{k}{i} (-1)^i$ in (5.1), at least for some k , e.g., if $p = 3$ or 5 .

In fact, for example, if k is even and $3 \nmid k$, we get that $\sum_{3|i} \binom{k}{i} (-1)^i = (-1)^{k/2+1} 3^{k/2-1}$. Theorem 5 provides us with a tool to calculate the ternary digits of $S(i(p-1)p^m, k)$ if $k \equiv 2$ or $4 \pmod{6}$. Its proof is a straightforward generalization of that of Theorem 4. We demonstrate its use in the next example.

Example 14. If $p = 3$ then $u_k \equiv b_k \equiv b_k^{-1} \pmod{3}$ is the least positive residue of the 3-free part b_k of $k!$ modulo 3 which is the same as that of its inverse modulo 3. For instance, if $k = 4$ we get then $b_4 = 8$, $u_k = 2$, $c_4 = -1$ and

$$a_4 = \left\lceil \frac{b_4}{3} \right\rceil = 3,$$

which yields that $b_4 = 9 - 1$. We obtain that

$$S(2i \cdot 3^m, 4) \equiv - \sum_{j=0}^r 3^{2j} \pmod{3^{e(m,4,r)}} \tag{5.3}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} e(m, 4, r) &= \min\left\{m + 1 - \frac{4 - d_3(4)}{2}, m + 1 + \nu_3(3) + \frac{d_3(4)}{2} - 1, \right. \\ &\quad \left. (r + 1)(1 + \nu_3(3)) + \frac{d_3(4)}{2} - 1\right\} \\ &= \min\{m, 2(r + 1)\}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that $S(2i \cdot 3^m, 4)$ ends in $(12)^*122$ in base 3.

Remark 15. Since $k! = 3^{\frac{k-d_3(k)}{2}} b_k = 3^{\frac{k-d_3(k)}{2}} (3a_k + c_k)$ we get the “best use” of Theorem 5 when a_k is a power of three, i.e., when $k!$ is the difference or sum of two powers of three. For example, in Example 14, $4! = 24 = 3^3 - 3$ leads to (5.3).

Remark 16. In a similar fashion to the case with $p = 3$, if $p = 5$ then we can use the fact that $\sum_{5|i} \binom{k}{i} (-1)^i$ can be expressed explicitly in terms of Fibonacci or Lucas numbers, with a formula depending on k modulo 20 (cf. [4]).

The idea of getting more p -ary digits of $S(i(p-1)p^m, k)$ by increasing m is well supported and the rate of increase is made effective by the following theorem which is based on Theorems 11 and 14 of [6]. This theorem can be used in getting the digits successively although not in a direct fashion as in (2.3), (2.4), and (5.3).

Theorem 17. *Let $p \geq 2$ be a prime, $c, n, k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $1 \leq k \leq p^n$ and $(c, p) = 1$, and u be a nonnegative integer, then*

$$\nu_p(S(cp^{n+1} + u, k) - S(cp^n + u, k)) \geq n - \lceil \log_p k \rceil + 2.$$

It was also conjectured in Conjecture 2 in [6] that for $n, k \in \mathbb{N}$, $3 \leq k \leq 2^n$, and $c \geq 1$ odd integer, we have

$$\nu_2(S(c2^{n+1}, k) - S(c2^n, k)) = n + 1 - f(k)$$

for some function $f(k)$ which is independent of n (for any sufficiently large n). In fact, for small values of k , numerical experimentation suggests that

$$f(k) = 1 + \lceil \log_2 k \rceil - d_2(k) - \gamma(k),$$

with $\gamma(4) = 2$ and otherwise it is zero except if k is a power of two or one less, in which cases $\gamma(k) = 1$. This would imply that $f(k) \geq 0$, cf. [6].

In connection with Theorem 12, we note that if k is divisible by $p - 1$ then k/p is not an odd integer. On the other hand, if k/p is an odd integer then we observe a behavior which is somewhat different from that of Theorem 12.

Theorem 18. (Theorem 2 in [4]) *For any odd prime p , if k/p is an odd integer then $\nu_p(k!S(i(p-1)p^m, k)) > m$.*

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